

Isomerisation of Methyl-naphthalenes over Acidic Chalcide Catalysts

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The catalytic vapour phase isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene and vice-versa was studied in the temperature range 420-620° and at varying liquid hourly space velocities on alumina-silica, alumina-chromia and alumina-boria of several molar compositions in flow systems using both fixed and fluidised bed conditions. The isomeric distribution of the products, as determined by a combination of spectroscopic and chromatographic methods, was found to be in conformity with the reported equilibrium values. Disproportionation, a competing parallel reaction during the isomerisation of methylbenzenes, did not occur in the case of methyl-naphthalenes although some dealkylation to naphthalene was observed at higher reaction temperatures, especially under fixed-bed conditions. The isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene apparently obeyed first order rate law with an energy of activation of about 26 k cal/mol, the value being close to those obtained with the xylenes. On the strength of the experimental evidence obtained, a mechanism involving the 1,2 shift of the methyl group through the formation of a localised π -complex intermediate has been postulated.

In an earlier report from this laboratory the kinetics and mechanism of intramolecular methyl migration in monocyclic aromatic systems were reported¹. In the present communication the concept has been extended to the bicyclic aromatic systems.

Experimental

Fixed-bed studies : The experimental set-up consisted of a 20 cm × 1.8 cm, silica reactor, a tubular furnace with thermostatic control, product collecting systems, mercury manometers and an aspirator bottle for gas collection. The feed was admitted into the reactor through a preheated zone and the reaction products were trapped in ice cooled condensers. The gaseous products were collected in an aspirator bottle over brine. No carrier gas was used.

Fluid-bed studies : The reaction was conducted in a fluid-bed glass reactor, size 120 cm × 3.8 cm containing 40 g of 60/100 B.S. mesh catalyst maintained in the fluidised state by sending-in dry nitrogen at the rate of 2.7 to 3.6 litre per minute at N.T.P. The feed vapours were, at the same time, carried to the reaction zone by bubbling a slow stream of dry nitrogen at the rate of 100-120 ml per minute at N.T.P. through the carburettor containing the feed. The feed rate could be controlled and regulated by proper adjustment of the nitrogen flow. The reaction products were condensed in an air condenser followed by a pair of ice cooled condensers.

Product analysis : Product analysis was accomplished by G.C., ir, and nmr spectroscopic measurements. The apparatus used were (i) a Perkin-Elmer, 421 double beam ir spectrophotometer with grating optics, (ii) a Varian A-60 analytical high resolution nmr spectrometer with built-in

integrator and (iii) a Chromacon 9580 gas chromatograph with Katharometer detector.

Results and Discussion

General product distribution : The isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene produced 2-methylnaphthalene together with naphthalene, 'coke' and gas as byproducts under fixed-bed catalytic conditions. Similarly a mixture of 1-methylnaphthalene, naphthalene, coke and gas was obtained when 2-methylnaphthalene was used as the feed. The isomerisation of a binary mixture of the mono-methylnaphthalenes resulted in enrichment of 2-methylnaphthalene till the composition of the catalysate was close to the equilibrium value containing about 70% 2-isomer. The gaseous products consisted of mainly hydrogen and methane besides ethane, ethylene, propane, propylene and carbon-monoxide.

The isomerisation was particularly favoured under fluid-bed catalytic conditions and it was observed in some runs made with a mixture of 1- and 2-methylnaphthalenes taken in their eutectic ratio (containing about 70% 1-isomer) that the isomeric distribution was altered involving a near reversal to yield the thermodynamic value of the two isomers (Fig. 1). The occurrence of side reactions, such as dealkylation or disproportionation was relatively much less under fluid-bed conditions. For example at 500° the amount of naphthalene, coke and gas formed under fluid-bed condition was only 4 percent in contrast to about 30 percent obtained in fixed-bed studies, over an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst.

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature on 1-methylnaphthalene conversion was studied at 480-580° over an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) as well

Fig. 1. Near reversal of isomeric ratios (Fluid Bed)
 Feed : mixture of 1 and 2-methylnaphthalene
 Catalyst : Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)
 Feed rate : $0.2 \text{ ml h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ of catalyst
 Carrier flow : 2.8 lit/min at NTP
 △ naphthalene; ○ 2-methylnaphthalene;
 □ 1-methylnaphthalene.

as an alumina-boria (11 : 1M) catalysts under fixed-bed conditions. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that on an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst the conversion to 2-methylnaphthalene showed little variation with rise in temperature and remained within 24-27% in almost all cases. The conversion of 1-methylnaphthalene over an alumina-boria (11 : 1M) catalyst was found to be relatively less. Over this catalyst the conversion of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene initially showed a sharp increase

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on conversion (Fixed Bed)
 Feed : 1-methylnaphthalene
 Catalysts : ○ Alumina-silica (1 : 15M);
 △ Alumina-boria (11 : 1M)
 LHSV : $0.4 \text{ ml h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ of catalyst. (W/F=860)

from 7.5 percent at 420° to 13.1 percent at 450° . Above 450° , however, the conversion progressively decreased till it dropped to 8.35% at 560° .

The catalytic conversion of 2-methylnaphthalene was studied on an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst

between 450° and 620° . The results are shown in Fig. 3. The conversion to 1-methylnaphthalene initially showed marginal increase from 15.3% at 450° to 19.0% at 480° and a marked tendency to decline thereafter till the conversion dropped to about 7% at 600° .

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on conversion (Fixed Bed)
 Feed : 2-methylnaphthalene
 Catalyst : Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)
 LHSV : $0.8 \text{ ml h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ of catalyst. (W/F=470)
 ○ 1-methylnaphthalene.

The effect of temperature on the course of reaction upon using the eutectic mixture of 1- and 2-methylnaphthalene (containing 70% 1-methylnaphthalene and 30% 2-methylnaphthalene) as the feed was studied over a number of alumina-silica and alumina-boria catalysts. It was observed that in general, isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene was favoured in the temperature range 450 - 520° . At higher temperatures side reactions, such as dealkylation leading to the formation of naphthalene, coke and gas predominated. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on conversion (Fixed Bed)
 Feed : Mixture of 1 and 2-methylnaphthalene
 Catalyst : Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)
 LHSV : $0.4 \text{ ml h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ of catalyst. (W/F=858)
 △ naphthalene; ○ 2-methylnaphthalene;
 □ 1-methylnaphthalene.

Effect of time factor W/F (g catalyst/mole feed/h) :
 The isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene was studied at ten different values of W/F ranging from 50 to 350, on an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst. It will be seen from Fig. 5 that the conversion of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene apparently increased with increase in W/F value upto 250 and declined thereafter owing to the occurrence of side reactions, such as dealkylation and cracking. The optimum conversion of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene was 36.7% at 500° and W/F having the value 250, when the catalysate comprised 40% 2-methylnaphthalene, 47% unreacted feed and 13% naphthalene.

Fig. 5. Effect of W/F (g. catalyst/mole feed/hr) on conversion
 Feed : 1-methylnaphthalene
 Catalyst : Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)
 Temperature : 500° ○ 2-methylnaphthalene.

The effect of W/F on the conversion of 2-methylnaphthalene showed almost a similar trend although the conversion values were relatively less than those obtained with 1-methylnaphthalene as the feed. Thus, at 500° the conversion of 2-methylnaphthalene to 1-methylnaphthalene was only 18.3% at W/F having the value 470 which reached the maximum value of 25% at W/F equal to 1420, when the catalysate contained 40% naphthalene and 40% 1-methylnaphthalene, the remaining being unconverted 2-methylnaphthalene.

Catalyst performance : Of all the catalysts tried an alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst was found to be most selective from the standpoint of isomerisation while an alumina-boria (3 : 1M) catalyst was possibly a better dealkylation catalyst.

The relative ratios of 2-methylnaphthalene to 1-methylnaphthalene in the catalysate obtained over different catalysts are presented in Table 1 which shows that the ratios are always in favour of the 2-isomer and mostly lie between 2 and 3. It is of interest to note that almost similar relative abundance of 2-methylnaphthalene is found in the products of coal carbonization and petroleum refining³. (In the case of xylenes the more stable *m*-xylene always predominates). The greater thermodynamic stability of the isomers of preponderance would

Compound	Density (g/ml)	Refractive Index n_D^{20}	Purity (%)	Source
1-methyl-naphthalene	1.0187 ³³	1.6176	99.0	Fluka A-6 Chemische Fabrik Bucks S. G. Switzerland
2-methyl-naphthalene	1.0000 ⁴⁰	1.6021	99.8	—do—
Mixed methyl-naphthalenes containing 70% (approx.) 1-isomer	1.0060 ³³	1.6013	—	—do—

suggest that these molecules are possibly reformed during coal carbonization and petroleum refining³.

Kinetic analysis of the data : 1-Methylnaphthalene \rightleftharpoons 2-Methylnaphthalene : The iso-

merisation of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene has been reported by earlier authors to be a simple first order reaction⁴. The present experimental evidence, however, strongly suggests the isomerisation to be a complex reversible reaction involving equilibration. The rate expression in the present study was accordingly computed by substituting the equilibrium conversion value, x_e in the place of initial concentration in the equation for a simple first order reaction⁵.

$$\text{Thus } \ln \left[\frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \right] = \frac{W}{F} (k_1 + k_2)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for the forward and reverse reactions.

$\log \left[\frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \right]$ when plotted against W/F was found

to be reasonably linear over the temperature range 500-525°, so that apparently the isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene can be said to obey a first order rate law. A typical plot is shown in Fig 6. The values of sum of the rate constants for the forward and reverse reactions were obtained from slopes of these graphs. The thermodynamic equilibrium value of 1.683 for the equilibrium constant (K) at 773° Kelvin for the reaction represents the ratio of k_1/k_2 ⁶. From these the individual values of k_1 and k_2 were determined and are presented in Table 3. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_1$ vs 1/T is shown in Fig. 7. The slope of the plot corresponded to a value of 26.12 k cal/mole as the apparent energy of activation for 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalene conversion. The experimentally determined value of 2.00 for the ratio of rate constants for the forward and reverse reaction obtained over alumina-silica (1 : 15M) catalyst (Table 2) was in close agreement with the calculated thermodynamic equilibrium value of 1.683.

Mechanism of isomerisation : The observed first order nature of the reaction and the near equivalence in the value for the activation energy to

Fig. 6. Plot of $\log [X_e/X_e - X]$ vs W/F (g catalyst/mole/ feed/hr)
 Feed : 1-methylnaphthalene
 Catalyst : Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)
 Temperature : \odot 500°; \triangle 510°; \square 525°.

Fig. 7. Arrhenius plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$
 $E = 26.12$ k cal/mole.

TABLE 2—RELATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF 1- AND 2-METHYLNAPHTHALENES IN DIFFERENT PRODUCTS

Source	Coal tar and petroleum fractions	Catalyst	Catalysate	2-isomer to 1-isomer ratio
H. T. tar (Bhilai)	2.8	Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)	fluid bed	2.0
E. G. R. tar (Neyveli)	3.0	Alumina-silica (1 : 15M)	fixed bed	2.0
Middle Oil (Neyveli)	3.0	Alumina-boria (3 : 1M)	fixed bed	2.5
D. N. O. (Shalimar)	2.0	Alumina-boria (6 : 1M)	fixed bed	3.1
D. N. O. (Durgapur)	3.1	Alumina-boria (11 : 1M)	fixed bed	1.3
D. N. O. (Rourkela)	2.7	Alumina-chromia (8 : 1M)	fixed bed	2.4
IOMEX (Barauni)	2.5			

TABLE 3—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT AND RATE CONSTANTS FOR 1-METHYLNAPHTHALENE CONVERSION

Feed : 1-methylnaphthalene : Partial pressure of feed : 1 atmosphere, catalyst : alumina-silica (1 : 15M), Temperature : 500-525°

Thermodynamic equilibrium constant	$k_1 + k_2 = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$	k_1	k_2
1.683	0.005527	0.003467	0.002060
1.683	0.003899	0.002446	0.001453
1.683	0.003142	0.001971	0.001171

that for the isomerisation of xylenes (25.66 k cal/mole) suggest that the nature of the protonated complex should not vary greatly in going from monocyclic to bicyclic systems. The comparative low acidity of the chalcide catalysts which are now generally accepted to have majority of Brönsted sites⁹ and the normally expected product pattern obtained points away from the postulation of a σ -complex intermediate*. In analogy to the isomerisation of the xylene, a localised π -complex intermediate, therefore, appears to be more probable in the methylnaphthalene isomerisation too, taking into consideration the existence of migrational barriers around the periphery of the bicyclic naphthalene nucleus¹⁰.

The postulated primary step in the isomerisation is, therefore, the rapid reversible addition of a proton presumably from the structurally bound hydroxyl groups in the catalyst mass to the aromatic substrate to form the corresponding conjugate acid designated as a localised π -complex. In the next step the methyl group takes the place of the proton in the π -complex which subsequently undergoes rearrangement through the rate determining 1,2-shift of the methyl group in the following manner :

The same mechanism, according to the principle of microscopic reversibility, should also be operative in the isomerisation of 2-methylnaphthalene to 1-methylnaphthalene. The occurrence of 70% of the 2-isomer at equilibrium would suggest that the isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene proceeds at a rate about twice as fast as that for the reverse reaction. On the basis of statistical considerations too, prima-facie it would appear that although the methyl group in the 1-methylnaphthalene molecule has cent percent chance of migrating to the 2-position, in the case of 2-methylnaphthalene there is only 66 : 33 chance of the methyl group going either to the 1 or the 3-position in the ring owing to bond

* It is known that σ -complex intermediates are more probable in the presence of excess Lewis acid catalysts where such reactions are usually of second order (first order each with respect to the reactant and the catalyst) giving rise to abnormal product composition guided mainly by the relative basicity of the hydrocarbons to the Lewis acid catalyst rather than the expected equilibrium pattern*.

fixation in the naphthalene structure¹¹. However, a migration from ring position 2 or 3 would not involve any structural alternations.

Summary and conclusions :

1. The isomerisation of 1-methylnaphthalene to 2-methylnaphthalenes is essentially a reversible reaction represented by the following unimolecular model :

2. The nearness in the values of activation energies for the isomerisation of methylnaphthalenes (26.12 k cal/mole) and xylenes (25.86 k cal/mole) suggests that the nature of the intermediate complex formed does not vary greatly in going from the monocyclic to bicyclic systems.

3. In the process of isomerisation over weakly acidic chalcide catalysts a localised π -complex intermediate appears more probable. The subsequent rearrangement involves the rate determining 1,2 shift of the methyl group.

4. The experimental value of 2 for the k_1/k_2 ratio obtained over alumina-silica catalyst (1 : 15M) between 500 and 525° is in good agreement with the calculated thermodynamic value of 1.683 which indicates that 1-methylnaphthalene isomerises at a rate about twice as fast as that for the 2-methylnaphthalene conversion. At the equilibrium point of this kinetically controlled reaction, the mixture contains about 63-65% 2-methylnaphthalene and 30-32% 1-methylnaphthalene, the composition being relatively unaffected by small changes in temperature (viz. 500-525°).

Symbols—

E	: Energy of activation.
F	: Feed rate (mole h ⁻¹)
k	: Rate constant
K	: Equilibrium constant
LHSV	: Liquid hourly space velocity (ml h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ of catalyst)
r	: Rate of reaction
T	: Temperature in absolute units
W	: Weight of the catalyst (g)
D.N.O.	: Drained naphthalene oil
IOMEX	: Aromatic extract from petroleum refinery
H.T. tar	: Tar from high temperature carbonization of coal
E.G.R. tar	: Neyveli lignite tar (first condensate).

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